

MOVING CoP design and implementation report

Authors: Blanca Casares (AEIDL), Miranda García (AEIDL), Massimiliano Assante (CNR), Pasquale Pagano (CNR)

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D1.3: MOVING CoP design and implementation report

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Authors	Blanca Casares (AEIDL), Miranda García (AEIDL), Massimiliano Assante (CNR), Pasquale Pagano (CNR)
Work Package Leader	WP1 - AEIDL
Project Coordinator	University of Cordoba

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Acronyms

AEIDL: European Association for Innovation in Local Development

CoP: Community of Practice

CSO: Civil Society Organisation

D: Deliverable

DoA: Description of Action

EC: European Commission

EU: European Union

GA: Grant Agreement

KoM: Kick-off Meeting

KPI: Key Performance Indicators

LEADER: Liaison Entre Actions de Développement de l'Économie Rurale

M: month

MAP: Multi-Actor Platform

MOVING: MOUNTAIN Valorisation through INterconnectedness and Green growth

MRL: Mountain Reference Landscape

MRR: Mountain Reference Region

NGO: Non-governmental organisation / Non-profit organisation

PDO: Protected Designation of Origin

PGI: Protected Geographical Indication

VC: Value Chain

VRE: Virtual Research Environment

WP: Work Package

Executive summary

The deliverable **D1.3 MOVING Community of Practice (CoP) design and implementation report** elaborates on the design and implementation of the MOVING CoP, with the aim of assessing its realisation and development during years 1 and 2. D1.3 has four specific objectives:

- Analyse the performance and engagement of the Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs) (regional and EU MAPs) in years 1 and year 2 towards achieving the MOVING and CoP objectives;
- Identify issues in the implementation of the work plan;
- Learn from the results achieved;
- Propose recommendations, identify areas for improvements, and design actions and follow-up steps to be taken by the project to improve the implementation of the CoP (regional and EU MAPs).

D1.3 may lead to an improved and more focused CoP work plan for the next two years including new proposals for actions. It will also lead to an improved Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) tool for MAPs.

This deliverable has been developed using a combination of methods for the analysis of the CoP as a whole (23 regional MAPs, 1 EU MAP and the involvement of external actors). The methodology includes: (i) the analysis of the performance and engagement of the regional MAPs using the M&E tool for regional MAPs; (ii) analysis of the performance and engagement of the EU MAP; (iii) analysis of the dedicated Virtual Research Environment (VRE) Labs and (iv) analysis of CoP results achieved and indicators included in the work plan.

To complement this analysis, two surveys were conducted: (1) in August 2021 addressed to project partners related to the EU MAP - Ideas and expectations and (2) during May and June 2022 addressed to project partners and EU MAP members (external stakeholders) on the MOVING CoP - Ideas and expectations.

Section 3 of the deliverable presents the MOVING CoP and its objectives.

Section 4 provides detailed information on Regional MAPs and section 5 on the EU MAP. These sections explain their composition, their performance and engagement (including, among other aspects, an analysis of barriers and challenges as well as strengths and opportunities) and the results of the monitoring of these MAPs.

In addition, section 5 presents the thematic areas and topics to focus upcoming EU MAP activities as well as the relevant knowledge, initiative, projects or experience to be shared among the members of the EU MAP.

Finally, section 6 compiles the main results of the CoP that respond to the indicators included in the DoA for the expected project impacts. It includes the progress up to M22 (June 2022).

1. Introduction

MOVING (MOUNTAIN Valorisation through INterconnectedness and Green growth) is a Horizon 2020 project (2020-2024) coordinated by the University of Cordoba, gathering 23 partner organisations.

The overall objective of MOVING is to **build capacities and co-develop relevant policy frameworks across Europe for the establishment of new or upgraded and upscaled value chains that contribute to the resilience and sustainability of mountain areas**. This will be done through a bottom-up participatory process with value chain actors, regional and European stakeholders, and policymakers. Over four years, MOVING will work to give regional and European stakeholders new collaborative tools for the definition of policies in mountain regions.

A core feature of the project is the creation and animation of a **Community of Practice (CoP)**. The MOVING CoP is understood as a **European-wide Science-Society-Policy interface** to engage stakeholders around resilience to climate change of mountain value chains. It will bring together interested stakeholders to contribute in the co-creation and validation of all research outputs delivered by MOVING.

This deliverable **D1.3 MOVING CoP design and implementation report** elaborates on the design and implementation of the MOVING CoP until M24 (August 2022), with the aim of assessing its realisation and development during years 1 and 2. The specific objectives are to:

- Analyse the performance and engagement of the Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs) (regional and EU MAPs) in years 1 and year 2 (M1 to M22)¹ towards achieving the MOVING and CoP objectives;
- Identify issues in the implementation of the work plan;
- Learn from the results achieved;
- Propose recommendations, identify areas for improvements, and design actions and follow-up steps to be taken by the project to improve the implementation of the CoP (regional and EU MAPs).

¹ The delivery date for the D1.3 is M24 (end of August). In order to be able to carry out an information extraction and subsequent analysis, as well as to collect input from project partners and MAPs coordinators, the period that will be analysed is from M1 to M22 (end of June).

2. Methodology

The **methodology to develop the D1.3 MOVING CoP design and implementation report has included:**

- Analysis of the performance and engagement of the regional Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs) using the Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) tool for regional MAPs completed in M17 (January 2022) and M22 (June 2022) by all MAP coordinators. Through this tool, quantitative and qualitative data have been collected relating to: (i) setting up the MAPs and MAP composition; (ii) activities (WP3, WP4 and WP6); and (iii) consultations and interviews (WP3 and WP4).
- Analysis of the performance and engagement of the EU MAP. It included an assessment of the set up and composition of the EU MAP and the activities carried out during the first reporting period (RP1), covering years 1 and 2 of the project.
- Analysis of the Virtual Research Environment (VRE) Labs for regional MAPs and for the EU MAP to know the level of use and interaction.
- Analysis of CoP results achieved that aimed to review the progress on the indicators foreseen in the Description of Action (DoA) associated with the CoP, as well as those included in the workplan for the EU MAP.
- Analysis of the survey results on EU MAP - Ideas and expectations. The survey was targeted at the project partners. A total of 20 responses were received during August 2021. This survey consisted of four sections:
 - Section 1: General information
 - Section 2: Expectations and experience of MOVING partners
 - Section 3: Participation in the EU MAP
 - Section 4: Suggestions of relevant stakeholders for the EU MAP.
- Analysis of the survey results on the MOVING Community of Practice (CoP) - Ideas and expectations. The survey was targeted at the project partners (especially MOVING Multi-Actor Platforms' coordinators, WP and task leaders and MOVING Support Team for Stakeholder Engagement) and the EU MAP members (external actors).

The purpose of this survey was to complement the information compiled from the analysis of the regional MAPs and the EU MAP. It collected information to better understand the implementation of the CoP. Furthermore, the responses of the survey will help to: (i) identify issues in the implementation of the CoP's workplan; (ii) learn from results achieved; and (iii) draw recommendations, identify areas of improvements, and design actions and follow-up steps to be taken by the project to improve the implementation of the CoP (regional and EU MAPs).

A total of 20 responses (75% from project partners and 25% from non-partners) were received during May and June 2022. The analysis of the survey results has been organised on two levels: Regional Multi-Actor Platforms and European Multi-Actor Platform.

In terms of **methodological limitations in the analysis of the design and progress of the CoP**, the following should be highlighted:

- **Differences among the 24 MAPs:** (a) 23 are at regional level and one is at European level, (b) some of the regional MAPs are newly created and in others their members knew each other before, (c) the number and typology of actors involved in each regional MAP differs due to the type of region or value chain selected, (d) the gender balance is different among them as well as the degree of youth participation.
- **Type of value chain selected:** there is a range of traditional and innovative value chains. In some cases, the selected VCs include global value chains and involve specifically regulated place-based designations (such as PDO). In other cases the VCs are local, regional or national.

Regarding the focal product and service, it varies between: meat (lamb, beef, Iberian ham); crops (carob, chestnut flour, olive oil, cereals, tomatoes); cheese (sheep, cow); bio-honey; alcohol (wine, whisky), tourism and public goods (biodiversity, agroecology).

- **Implementation of planned activities:** between years 1 and 2, all regional MAPs have individually carried out tasks 3.3, 4.3 and 4.4 (see details in the section 4.2.2 Implementation of activities of this report). Only a couple of regional MAPs have exceptionally combined two tasks in one event or need to develop the last task 4.4 in September 2022.

At another level, EU MAP has carried out activities at European level which can be found in the section 5.2.2 Implementation of activities of this report.

- **Geographical scope of work:** some of the regional MAPs work at the level of:
 - Mountain Reference Regions (MRR). It refers to mountain areas where the project will roll-out its research activities according to the specification in the project proposal.
 - Mountain Reference Landscape (MRL). It refers to a smaller scale of work, usually at the local level, located within the Mountain Reference Region.

3. MOVING Community of Practice

MOVING's definition of the CoP is based on that of Wenger *et al.* (2002)² as “a group of people who share a concern, a set of problems, or a passion about a topic, and who deepen their knowledge and expertise in this area by interacting on an ongoing basis”. According to Wenger, the Communities of Practice usually involve multiple levels of participation based on perspectives, needs, and ambitions.

For the MOVING CoP the categories of membership and participation are: (i) core group; (ii) active participants; and (iii) occasional participants.

- **Core group:** a relatively small group of people whose passion and engagement energise and nurture the community;
- **Active participants:** members who are recognised as practitioners and define the community (though they may not be of one mind as to what the community is about);
- **Occasional/associated participants:** members who only participate when the topic is of special interest, when they have something specific to contribute, or when they are involved in specific activity. People who have a sustained connection to the community but with less engagement. Outsiders who interact with the community occasionally without being members themselves.

The **MOVING CoP** is the core forum for two-way peer exchanges of ideas for co-learning and co-creation of knowledge with different stakeholders (MOVING partners and externals to the project) and at different territorial level (regional and European). The conceptualisation of the MOVING CoP is transferred into practice through the creation of Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs), that provide the space for interaction, exchange and learning with stakeholders of the community at all territorial levels (regional and European). Hence, MOVING will create, animate and facilitate a total of 24 MAPs across Europe:

- **23 regional MAPs**, established in the 23 Reference Regions (see distribution and description on MOVING website: <https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference-regions/>);
- **1 EU MAP.**

Hence, the MOVING CoP is conceived as a nested structure of MAPs with different levels of interaction in the project.

² Wenger E, McDermott R, Snyder WM (2002). *Cultivating communities of practice: a guide to managing knowledge*. Harvard Business School Publishing, Cambridge.

Figure 1. Structure of the MOVING CoP

Source: MOVING H2020

Following the integrated transdisciplinary approach of the MOVING project, the MAPs provide a platform and space to engage with relevant stakeholders in the different activities of the project. This allows the exchange of knowledge and peer learning between stakeholders from the Reference Regions (RR) up to the European level.

It requires a sound management of the MAPs that involves different partners from the project.

- **Regional MAPs:** Coordinators of each of the Reference Regions (MOVING partners) coordinate, animate and facilitate the regional MAPs and implement the necessary activities. They also act as key contact points for their MAP, to facilitate the exchange of information and experiences with the other regional MAPs and the EU MAP.
- **EU MAP:** the European Association for Innovation in Local Development (AEIDL) manages and coordinates the EU MAP and its activities, animating and facilitating interaction between members. AEIDL supports the appropriate inclusion of the members and provides a balanced mix of activities in the MOVING CoP that are significant for the members. In addition, it is responsible for accepting new members to the CoP.
- **MOVING Support Team on Stakeholder Engagement:** A group of experts from the MOVING consortium that developed specific guidelines on stakeholder engagement to support regional MAPs in the creation, set-up and management of the MAPs.
- **MOVING Support Team on Workshop Facilitation:** A group of experts from the MOVING consortium that developed specific guidelines on workshop facilitation to support regional MAPs.

3.1. Objectives of the MOVING CoP

The objectives of the MOVING CoP are to:

- Bring together a community that contributes to the **co-creation and validation of key research outputs and results delivered by MOVING**;
- Foster the **exchange of knowledge and experience** that enhances joint learning and expertise on mountain value chains;
- Build a **long-lasting community** with MOVING stakeholders that is recognised as an important forum for issues around mountain value chains.

3.2. Typology and representation of actors in the CoP

At the beginning of the project, a typology of actors for the CoP has been established at both regional MAPs and EU MAP level.

The monitoring and evaluation tool for MAPs, explained in section 4.3 Monitoring the Regional MAPs of this deliverable, helps to collect the information following these categories and allows for the identification of unrepresented groups. Sections 4.1 and 5.1, of this deliverable, include a detailed analysis of the composition of the MAPs. The following Table 1 shows the categories used to classify MAP members and their representation in percentage.

Table 1. Typology of actors in the MOVING MAPs members and representation of each group

Type of actors in the Regional MAPs	Representation (%)	Type of actors in the EU MAP	Representation (%)
Public authority/policy-maker	18%	Public authority/policy-maker (local, regional, national)	8%
Researcher	14%	Researcher	54%
Business (agricultural, agri-food, forestry)	17%	Business (agricultural, agri-food, forestry)	2%
Business (diversified or non-agricultural businesses)	7%	NGO (local, regional, national, european)	15%
Innovation broker/advisor	7%	Civil Society Organisation (local, regional, national, european)	11%
Producer & producers associations	23%	Advisor/Innovation broker/intermediary	4%

NGO/CSO	6%	EU-funded projects (H2020, Horizon Europe, LIFE, Interreg, etc.)	2%
Civil Society	3%	Other	4%
Other	5%	European institutions (EC, EP, EESC, CoR, etc)	-
		Producer & producers associations	-
		Business (diversified or non-agricultural businesses)	
		EIP-AGRI Operational Group	-
		LEADER Local Action Group	-
		Citizens	-

Source: MOVING H2020

The typology of actors was defined based on the need to report on some indicators included in the DoA for the project's impact, as well as in agreement with the project's WPs leaders. Each category has been explained and exemplified in the tool's instructions and discussed with partners in three internal drop-in sessions to learn how to fill it in. In the planned update of the M&E tool for MAPs after M24, it is foreseen to group for regional MAPs reporting the civil society category with NGO/CSO.

Furthermore, at the regional MAP level it is recorded: the gender (male, female or other); age (<25, 25-40, >40); level of participation (core group, active participant or occasional/associated participant) and the area covered (local/MRL, regional/MRR, national and other). In addition, the [dedicated webpages of each Reference Region](#) include a section that describes the MAPs members per region/selected value chain. This information will be updated after M24 to further concretise the actors in case the regional MAPs require it.

For the EU MAP, the [expression of interest](#) includes in the typology of organisation/stakeholders a series of categories as indicated in Table 1.

A more detailed analysis of the composition of the MAPs is provided in sections 4 and 5 of this report as well as what conclusions and action points are drawn to reinforce the under-represented groups at the level of typology, gender, age and area covered.

4. Regional Multi-Actor Platforms

The 23 regional Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs) are established in the [23 Reference Regions](#) from 16 countries. These regions represent the wide diversity of mountain areas in Europe and neighbouring countries. Each of the regional MAPs are implemented and facilitated by the coordinators of each of the Reference Regions.

Figure 2. Distribution of MOVING Reference Regions

Source: MOVING H2020

4.1. Composition

The coordinators of each region and MAP are responsible for attracting and involving relevant stakeholders in the activities to be conducted by MOVING within the respective Reference Region. They are responsible for identifying, selecting and involving the relevant stakeholders. The composition of the MAPs differs from one another within MOVING so as to adapt to the interests and contexts of the Reference Regions.

MAPs are open for the participation of relevant stakeholders, including those from the consortium partners and also external actors who can add value to the work and dynamics of the MAP. One starting point for the identification of the key MAP stakeholders might be the nature of the activities and work to be conducted within the MAP under the various Work Packages. It is important that the key stakeholders participate in the activities of the project so each MAP can produce the best research outcomes possible, following the guidance and direction of the relevant WP / Task leaders. Hence, not all the members of the MAPs will be expected to contribute to all the activities.

Table 2 describes the Regional Multi-Actor Platform members in a qualitative way.

Table 2. Regional Multi-Actor Platform members

Reference Region / regional MAP	Members of the Regional Multi-Actor Platform (MAP)
Austrian Alps	The MAP brings together different stakeholders, such as representatives of regional development (LEADER and other structures), the cooperative of sheep farmers from the region of Weiz, other farmers, public authorities, innovators and regional business actors, as well as interest groups.
Stara Planina (Bulgaria)	The MAP comprises a diversity of stakeholders: public authorities and policymakers, researchers (University of National and World Economy, Sofia), producers (traditional local farmers – mainly small-scale semi-subsistence pastoralism and innovative local farmers), agricultural business and non-agricultural business, advisors, NGOs, civil society and Local Action Groups.
Šumava – Cesky Les (Czechia)	The MAP brings together local farmers and processors that are directly engaged in the researched value chain, alongside farmers' associations, local and regional authorities (represented by mayors and representatives of the Pilsen Region), non-profit organisations focused on environmental protection and local development (such as Local Action Groups).
Corsica (France)	The MAP is the result of a partnership between the three municipalities of Bucugnà, Ghisoni and Nuceta and researchers from INRAE (LRDE-UMR Selmet). It is part of a larger project led by a group of municipalities (GAL-Leader, and communities of municipalities) in central Corsica. The project relies on professional organisations in the sector, regional institutions and institutional actors involved in chestnut groves. The integration of local tourism and commercial operators is planned to support actions to promote and enhance the project.
Drome Valley (France)	The MAP consists of pastoral and sheep meat experts such as technical supporting structures, local authorities (municipalities, departments, etc.), National Park, researchers, breeders and groups of breeders, local slaughter houses and butchers, local supply actors and other relevant actors.
Crete (Greece)	The MAP brings together farmers who cultivate carob and farmers who harvest self-planted trees, academics with a research interest in carob, the Regional Directorates of Agriculture, Rural Development and Forestry, Carob processing plants and businesses, and carob cultural institutions and initiatives.
Transdanubian Mountains (Hungary)	The MAP consists of producers, NGOs, members of civil society, public authorities/policymakers, business representatives (both agricultural and non-agricultural) and researchers.
Central Apennines (Italy)	The MAP gathers 24 actors: 7 public authorities/policymakers, 9 producers (e.g. farmers, livestock farmers, and forest managers), 3 NGOs, 1 innovation broker/advisor, 1 business actor (agricultural) and 1 civil society representative.

Eastern Alps (Italy)	The MAP includes vine-growers and other farmers, advisors, leading private and cooperative wine companies (Ferrari and others), local environmental associations (NGOs), local research institutes, and representatives of Provincial Directorate of Agriculture. It is also planned to involve local tourism agencies and other associations.
Northern Apennines (Italy)	The MAP gathers 15 actors: 5 public authorities/policymakers, 4 researchers, 3 producers (e.g. farmers, livestock farmers and forest managers), 3 NGOs, 2 innovation brokers/advisors and 1 civil society representative.
Maleshevski mountains (North Macedonia)	The MAP brings together representatives from the business sector, public authorities, NGOs, individual producers and civil society.
Cordilheira central (Portugal)	The MAP is involving actors from diverse areas of activity, directly or indirectly linked to the Serra da Estrela PDO cheese VC: shepherds of the Bordaleira da Serra da Estrela sheep breed, associations of commons, cheesemakers, nature tourism agents, representatives of the PDO cheese producers' cooperative and public bodies.
Maciço Noroeste (Portugal)	The MAP includes different actors, such as vine and wine producers of different sizes and types, other farming actors, local cultural associations, public authorities, innovation brokers, tourist companies, researchers and regional business actors as well as interest groups.
Southern Romanian Carpathian mountains (Romania)	The MAP will comprise a diversity of stakeholders, such as public authorities and policymakers (Piatra Craiului National Park Administration, National Mountain Area Agency, National Agency for Protection of the Environment and local Mayor's offices), researchers (Transilvania University of Braşov), NGOs (Association of Ecotourism in Romania, WWF – Danube Carpathian Programme, Mountain Guides and Mountain Leaders Society, and local development NGOs), producers (small-scale farmers, grassland managers and foresters), business (local accommodation providers, traditional/artisan food producers), local guides, providers of specialist activities and other eco-tour operators), innovation brokers/advisors, and Local Action Groups.
Dinaric Mountains (Serbia)	The MAP in Sjenica and Pester Plateau brings together different actors representing local, regional and national institutions and authorities, organisations, advisors, academics and researchers.
Slovak Carpathian mountains (Slovakia)	The MAP includes beekeepers and honey producers in mountain areas, producers' associations, business representatives (both agricultural and non-agricultural), researchers, representatives of NGOs, public authorities, and other interested members of civil society.
Betic Systems (Spain)	The MAP includes members of four groups: i) producers and companies; ii) associations, NGOs, citizens; iii) organisations, institutions, and research projects; iv) government and municipalities; and v) external experts.

Sierra Morena (Spain)	The MAP is composed of the key actors of the Iberian ham value chain, which includes pig breeders, producers, landowners, researchers, technicians, public authorities, businesses, cooperatives, PDO actors, NGOs, and civil society. It also aims to focus on the interactions of this VC with other traditional and innovative VCs rooted in the dehesas (e.g. cork production and astronomy tourism).
Spanish Pyrenees (Spain)	The MAP gathers different stakeholders from regional development (LEADER and other structures), winery cooperative from the region of Hoya de Huesca, public authorities, other farmers, innovators and regional business actors.
Swiss Alps (Switzerland)	The MAP is still under construction and currently involves actors from all parts of the value chain, such as government officials at cantonal and municipal levels, researchers, local nature park and – very important – representatives of the GranAlpin label, including grain producers. In the future, the platform hopes to include processing plants (mills and silos), tourism and gastronomy sectors, as well as local business actors.
Swiss Jura (Switzerland)	The MAP is being formed. To be added when available.
Beydaglari (Turkey)	The MAP comprises about 20 stakeholders related to the value chain, including the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry in Elmali District; Elmali Chamber of Farmers; Chamber of Commissioners; Agricultural Cooperatives; tomato growers; West Mediterranean Agricultural Research Institute; Elmali Municipality; Water User Association; Vocational School of Elmali; The Union of West Mediterranean Exporters.
Highlands and Islands (UK-Scotland)	The core stakeholders of the MAP have formed a Stakeholder Advisory Group, which includes producers, NGOs, members of civil society, public authority/policymakers, business representatives (both agricultural and non-agricultural) and researchers.

Source: MOVING H2020

Identifying and involving the right type of stakeholders within the activities of the MAP is essential for the success of the MOVING project. In this respect, support is provided to the MAPs by the respective WP / Task leaders in relation to the type of relevant stakeholders to be identified or involved in the specific activities.

Moreover, the Support Team for Stakeholder Engagement provides guidance on how to identify the relevant actors to be engaged in the MAPs, also in relation to the nature and needs of the activities of each of the project WPs.

The monitoring and evaluation tool for regional MAPs, explained in section 4.3 Monitoring the Regional MAPs of this deliverable, has made it possible to track and collect the total number of members of the 23 regional MAPs (by type of actor, distribution by gender, by age, by area covered and by level of participation). The following figures represent the quantitative information related to the total number of members of the 23 regional MAPs.

The total number of members of the 23 regional MAPs is 766 stakeholders of which 69% are men and 31% are women. The gender balance is different between the 23 regional MAPs: the regional MAP with the lowest representation of women is with 12% and the regional MAP with the highest with 61% of women.

Figure 3 shows the distribution of the total number of members in different stakeholder categories. As can be seen, the most represented types of actors are: producers and producers associations; public authorities and policy makers; business from agriculture and researchers.

Figure 3. Regional MAPs' composition (type of actor, =766)

Source: MOVING H2020

The following figures show the total number of members of the regional MAPs by: a. (Figure 4) geographic area of influence (local or reference landscape, regional or reference region, national and other); b. (Figure 5) level of participation and involvement (core group, active participants and occasional or associated participants) and c. (Figure 6) age (under 25, 25 to 40 and over 40 years of age).

Figure 4. Regional MAPs' composition (area covered, =766)

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 5. Regional MAPs' composition (level of participation, =766)

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 6. Regional MAPs' composition (participants' age, = 766)

Source: MOVING H2020

In addition, **the monitoring and evaluation tool for regional MAPs has made it possible to collect the reflections of the 23 MAP coordinators on the process and state of composition** of the regional MAPs and how this affects the engagement of the members in the different project tasks.

As presented above, all types of stakeholders are represented in the regional MAPs, but there are some groups that are considered challenging to include or are less represented in the MAPs. The regional MAPs said these were: (i) business, retailers, processors and distributors; (ii) farmers and land managers; (iii) public sector, especially policymakers from the national level; (iv) young people; (v) women (gender relations-representation in the sector); and (vi) NGO/CSOs and other civil society organisations, as well as groups representing consumers' views.

Regional MAPs were asked about actions needed to create a more balanced representation in their MAP:

- Simplification of concepts and terms, so that the stakeholders can understand better the project.
- Identify and contact people from unrepresented groups.
- It would be very useful to be able to make informal visits to farmers to explain the project and invite them to join the MAP.
- Take advantage of interviews to strengthen the MAP.

- Working with specialised technical services (e.g. animal registration, veterinarians, crop advisors) was shown to be successful in getting in touch with producers (e.g. young people), so include them in project activities.
- Approach young people (secondary schools, universities).
- Approach women and in particular female farmers.
- Adjust the timing of workshops to when farmers do not have harvesting and field care tasks.
- Change the venue to facilitate more participation.
- Identify some practical MOVING outcomes that will reinforce engagement.
- Clarify that different business models are not necessarily in conflict.
- Create opportunities for work and dialogue with actors such as natural parks, national organisations or scientists and nature protection associations.
- Invitations to project activities should be issued well in advance so that the various actors can participate. A calendar of activities is needed to allow MAP members to see what activities are planned for the year.

Finally, in relation to composition, they were asked to identify the most important lessons learnt. The MAP coordinators highlighted:

- Longer set-up period for MAP establishment is needed.
- There are many different perceptions and discourses, each with its own rationale. It is important to contextualise these perceptions and discourses according to the actors' profiles and thus give them an interpretation within the map of relationships.
- The importance of building trust between different MAP members to ensure the smooth functioning and achievement of common objectives in the MAP. In addition, the importance of mediation and the need to reduce the chances of conflicts among MAP members or conflicting issues (such as management models).
- The usefulness of listening to different points of view in order to bring together the criteria of the regional MAP members.
- It is very important to have, as MAP coordinators, a cohesive plan and to set clear and realistic expectations. Involving a large and diverse group of people is a challenge, as participants brought multiple, diverse and pressing issues and knowledge gaps.
- Link MOVING MAP objectives to the real needs of the participants and mountain community.

- It is important to maintain an ongoing relationship, through close communication and discussion (not only in project activities) with regional MAP members, and to think of valuable content for the meeting to keep stakeholders motivated.
- More field work and in-person meetings are needed to improve engagement.
- It is necessary to increase connection with other regional MAPs and the EU MAP (regional, national and international perspective).
- There are local actors who want to cooperate and collaborate to improve the VC and contribute to the sustainability and resilience of the region.

4.2. Performance and engagement

This section outlines the activities that all the regional MAPs had conducted with their members over the course of the first 22 months of the project.

4.2.1. Setting up the regional MAPs

This initial activity is an important step in achieving a smooth start to the MAP, by raising awareness, generating interest and ensuring appropriate stakeholder engagement from the beginning. A MOVING expert support team produced guidelines for regional MAPs, helping them to develop meaningful and sustainable stakeholder engagement, and to elaborate activities to raise awareness. This creative process embraced four principles: 1) flexible programming; 2) co-construction; 3) multi-level interactions; and 4) impartiality and transparency.

Some of the 23 regional MAPs organised kick-off meetings with their MAP members before starting the workshops related to mandatory project tasks. In these kick-off activities, the regional MAP coordinators collected the participants' expectations of being part of the MAP:

- Share common problems.
- Exchange knowledge, acquire new information and learn from other experiences (at MAP level and from other regional MAPs).
- Create new network and contacts, in particular, to meet other (remote) local actors.
- Better understand local dynamics and identities, the different roles of value chain (VC) actors in the region.
- High interest in the selected value chain and specific topics such as climate protection, adaptation initiatives, rural and regional development, etc.
- Possibility to express their own perspective on the functioning of the VC.
- Contribute collectively to find solutions and practical results related to quality-of-life of farmers, well-being of mountain communities, and improved local socio-economic conditions, and obtain a clear vision for the future of the value chain and the region.

- Propose policy recommendations.
- Ensure future collaboration with other VC actors and share more common projects that contribute to the sustainable development of the area.

Each of the regional MAPs selected one of the value chains to analyse in detail throughout the project, from those mapped in the Mountain Value Chains Inventory (D4.1). Table 3 compiles the value chain of each of the project regions and links to their dedicated web page.

Table 3. Regional Multi-Actor Platforms and their selected value chains

Reference Region / regional MAP	Selected value chain	More information
Austrian Alps	Sheep farmers from the region of Weiz	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/austrian-alps-austria/
Stara Planina (Bulgaria)	Public Goods from High Nature Value Farming	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/stara-planina-bulgaria/
Šumava – Cesky Les (Czechia)	Cattle	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/sumava-cesky-les-czechia/
Corsica (France)	Chestnut Flour	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/corsica-france/
Drome Valley (France)	Sheep meat locally produced and valorised	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/drome-valley-france/
Crete (Greece)	Central Rethymno Carob	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/crete-greece/
Transdanubian Mountains (Hungary)	Agroecological Knowledge	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/transdanubian-mountains-hungary/
Central Apennines (Italy)	Alto-Molise Dairy	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/central-apennines-italy/
Eastern Alps (Italy)	Trento Doc Wine	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/eastern-alps-italy/

Northern Apennines (Italy)	Chestnut Flour	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/northern-apennines-italy/
Maleshevski mountains (North Macedonia)	Rural Tourism	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/maleshevski-mountains-north-macedonia/
Cordilheira central (Portugal)	Serra da Estrela PDO Cheese	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/cordilheira-central-portugal/
Maciço Noroeste (Portugal)	Douro Wine	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/macico-noroeste-portugal/
Southern Romanian Carpathian mountains (Romania)	Certified ecotourism	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/southern-romanian-carpathian-mountains-romania/
Dinaric Mountains (Serbia)	Dinaric Alps: Sjenica lamb PDO	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/dinaric-mountains-serbia/
Slovak Carpathian mountains (Slovakia)	Bio-honey	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/slovak-carpathian-mountains-slovakia/
Betic Systems (Spain)	Organic Olive Oil	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/betic-systems-spain/
Sierra Morena (Spain)	Los Pedroches PDO Iberian Ham	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/sierra-morena-spain/
Spanish Pyrenees (Spain)	Mountain Wine	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/spanish-pyrenees-spain/
Swiss Alps (Switzerland)	Mountain Grain	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/swiss-alps-switzerland/
Swiss Jura (Switzerland)	Tête de Moine PDO cheese	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/swiss-jura-switzerland/
Beydaglari (Turkey)	Greenhouse Tomato	Website: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/beydaglari-turkey/

Highlands and Islands (UK-Scotland)	Speyside Malt Whisky	<u>Website:</u> https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/highlands-and-islands-uk-scotland/
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Source: MOVING H2020

4.2.2. Implementation of activities

The information provided in Table 4 below provides an overview of the scope of work conducted by the regional MAPs under each WP until the end of M22 (June 2022).

Table 4. Regional MAPs activities during the first half of the project

WP	Description
WP1 Integrating research with Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task 1.1 Dissemination, exploitation, communication and outreach strategy. Support the implementation of the DECO Strategy (e.g. communicate about the activities and results of the MAPs in conferences, writing articles, news on the website, etc.). • Task 1.4 Virtual Research Environment (VRE). Share information about the MAPs, and if relevant, create and manage the VRE for the regional MAPs. • Task 1.5 Engaging young people in MOVING activities.
WP3 Development of visual science-society-policy interface tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task 3.3 Participatory vulnerability analysis of land systems. Validation of the susceptibility levels to climate change and other threats. It will take place across the reference regions, gathering information and local knowledge from selected experts and citizens. The identification of productivity thresholds will be done using a two-step process: 1) consultation with 8-10 experts, as well as local actors such as farmers and forestry owners; 2) a participatory workshop with a broad range of stakeholders, for the validation of the susceptibility levels identified in T3.2, as well of the vulnerability matrixes based on the expert consultation, and for identifying gaps of information on key drivers/threats.
WP4 Participatory appraisal of vulnerability and performance of value chains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task 4.3 Extended value chain analysis. Semi-structured interviews. For the extended value chain analysis, data will be sourced from: a) existing secondary data via desktop reviews and analysis of datasets; b) 15-20 semi-structured interviews with the main actors involved in the VC assemblage. • Task 4.4 Participatory workshops in each region. The results of task 4.3 will be presented to each regional MAP in a face-to-face workshop as a preliminary concept 'map' of the VC and the system. Participants will use their local knowledge to update our understanding and show if gaps remain in how the system and the value chain co-exist. They will also be useful inputs to WP6 and the generation of the baseline scenario.

Source: MOVING H2020

Table 5 shows the main figures of regional MAPs activities in Year 1 and 2. It includes for tasks 3.3, 4.3 and 4.4 (both workshops and stakeholder consultations) the number of events organised, the number of participants, the number of stakeholders interviewed, the distribution by gender, by age and by geographical area covered or area of influence. In turn, Table 6 gives the detail for the same tasks (3.3, 4.3 and 4.4) of the percentage of the type of stakeholder that has participated.

Table 5. Main figures of regional MAPs activities in Year 1 and 2

Task	Number of events	Number of participants	Number of stakeholders interviewed	Distribution by gender	Distribution by age	Distribution by area covered
Task 3.3 Participatory Workshop on vulnerability analysis of land systems	23	283	-	69% Men 31% Women	<25 – 5% 25-40 – 24% >40 – 72%	RL – 59% RR – 31% National 10% Other – 0%
Task 3.3 Consultation of 8-10 experts, as well as local actors as farmers and forestry owners	23	-	290	71% Men 29% Women	-	RL – 52% RR – 34% National 14% Other – 0%
Task 4.3 Extended value chain analysis	23	-	355	68% Men 26% Women 6% Other	-	RL – 64% RR – 23% National 13% Other – 0%
Task 4.4 Participatory Workshops in each region	21 ³	278	-	67% Men 33% Women	<25 – 6% 25-40 – 28% >40 – 66%	RL – 59% RR – 30% National 8%

³ The regional MAPs of the Austrian Alps (Austria) and Corsica (France) will carry out this task in the coming months.

						Other – 3%
Other non-mandatory events (meetings, discussion groups, KoM, visits)	25	-	-	-	-	-
Total activities	115	561	645	68% Men 30% Women 2% Other	<25 – 6% 25-40 – 25% >40 – 69%	RL – 59% RR – 29% National 11% Other – 1%

Source: MOVING H2020

Table 6. Percentage of type of stakeholders in the regional MAPs activities in Year 1 and 2

Task	Task 3.3 Participatory Workshop on vulnerability analysis of land systems	Task 3.3 Consultation of 8-10 experts, as well as local actors as farmers and forestry owners	Task 4.3 Extended value chain analysis	Task 4.4 Participatory Workshops in each region	Total activities
Public authority/policy-maker	18%	16%	15%	16%	16%
Researcher	18%	18%	12%	15%	15%
Business (agricultural)	15%	18%	20%	14%	17%
Business (diversified or non-agricultural businesses)	6%	7%	13%	7%	9%
Innovation broker/advisor	9%	11%	8%	12%	10%

Producer & producers associations	20%	21%	22%	19%	20%
NGO/CSO	8%	5%	4%	7%	6%
Civil society	2%	2%	2%	6%	3%
Other	4%	2%	4%	4%	4%

Source: MOVING H2020

Some conclusions related to the reinforcement of under-represented groups in regional MAPs and the point of actions that can be concluded are:

- More involvement of specialised technical services (e.g. animal registration, veterinarians, crop advisors) is required in order to get in touch with producers (e.g. young farmers) and advisors.
- Reach out to young people (high schools, universities). The Task 1.5 workshop will be key to improving the involvement of young people in the MAPs. The workshops in each region will take place between July and October 2022.
- Reach out to women and in particular women farmers.
- Establish more contacts with actors relevant to the region and the MAP but of national character.

For all the different activities, the regional MAP coordinators were asked to reflect on a number of questions:

MAP coordinators were first asked **how the composition of workshop participation influenced the workshops**. Their reflections include:

- More than half of the coordinators indicated that the composition of the MAP did not particularly influence the evolution of the workshop.
- Others said that there was a marked absence of young people and women. Also, on some occasions, farmers were at the last minute unable to attend due to their work.
- A couple of MAP coordinators indicated that the presence of a large number of public administration representatives (local and regional) reduced the potential to add information and comments from the audience.
- In the absence of some stakeholders, the coordinating MAPs held separate bilateral virtual meetings with them. However, this did not contribute to group building and the establishment of common ground.

- Some regions organised the workshops within a congress, which explains a relatively high percentage of researchers forming the group. This facilitated the presentation of MOVING's methodological approach.

Coordinators were asked **how MAP members interact and whether new relationships or networks were formed**. The responses reflect that:

- All coordinators responded that the relationship between MAP members is very constructive and positive. There are good ongoing discussions and the possibility of new connections. Some participants already knew each other, while for others it was an opportunity to meet new people.
- For many regions, even though MAP stakeholders had previously interacted for many years, they have not had the opportunity to be part of a wider community/network that can provide support and function as a forum for mutual concerns and develop collective understanding.
- The organisation of these workshops in MOVING is seen as an opportunity to form a new network. For example, researchers from nearby universities were not working in these specific mountain areas and new contacts have been established.

The MAP coordinators were also asked to reflect on **the extent to which the selected methodology was suitable for the objective**. Their reflections include:

- Most of them considered that the methodology was suitable for the objectives of the workshops. However, some terms required simpler explanations, and also a specific adaptation in terms of content. In particular, specific sections of the methodology were difficult to discuss with stakeholders, for example, the sensitivity questionnaire.
- Overall, the evaluation of the participants was positive.

Regarding other **elements that worked well**, the coordinators highlighted the commitment among the participants. They also stressed that:

- There is an interest and desire to continue participating in project activities and to contribute to the sustainability of the value chain and the region.
- There is a lot of interest to meet MAP members and exchange experiences. The interactive discussions were very proactive and open. The members expressed their appreciation for being selected for this project as it enhances the focus on this region.
- The project video as well as the prepared materials and presentations were appreciated.
- In the second workshop, the presentation of the results facilitates and drew attention to the main issues to be addressed.

Finally, as general questions about the development of the activities, coordinators were asked **what they would do differently next time**.

- Some of the coordinators reflected on resources and organisation. Discussion spaces and group work are very interesting, but time-consuming. There is a need to be less ambitious in the workshop objectives, especially when organising online meetings.
- In terms of dynamics to facilitate the participation of all members, it is necessary to ensure that not only the most knowledgeable participants express their concerns.
- It was felt that face-to-face meeting would be better and necessary to generate better engagement, but it is understood that the first workshops had to be online given COVID.
- It is important to keep working to ensure participation of more actors from different groups.
- It may be necessary to change the start time, to the evening or on a weekend, and the time of the year, to avoid farmers' harvesting work.

In **task 3.3 Participatory Workshop on vulnerability analysis of land systems**, MOVING focused on the vulnerability analysis on one key value chain (VC) per region. Specifically, the aim was to assess in a participatory way the vulnerability of the land use system providing key resources for the VC selected in each Mountain Reference Landscape (MRL) to critical drivers of change in a 20-year scenario.

The vulnerability matrices developed for the 23 MRLs in this task is probably the most comprehensive analysis of vulnerability of mountain land-use systems in Europe done to date. Through active engagement of more than 500 stakeholders across mountain regions in Europe we managed to obtain the perception of farmers, managers, extension officers and researchers on the relevance of drivers of change shaping the vulnerability of the systems.

In relation to **task 3.3 MAPs coordinators were asked to explain:**

How they administered the questionnaire and whether this questionnaire helped to generate more engagement. Their responses include:

- Most coordinators distributed the questionnaire in an online format. Some found it difficult to collect information using the online questionnaire, as people seemed to be overwhelmed with electronic communications.
- Some stakeholders were also contacted by phone to encourage them to fill in the questionnaire.
- A few coordinators completed a face-to-face questionnaire before the workshop started. During the workshop, the result of the ranking of the drivers was shared and discussed with the stakeholders.

The MAP coordinators were asked if they **obtained stakeholders' perceptions of trends (participatory exposure) and sensitivity of drivers.** Their reflections include:

- All coordinators indicated that they did, using both the questionnaire and the workshop. For some it was difficult to explain the difference between the questions on participatory exposure, vulnerability and sensitivity given the similarity and subtlety between terms.

- For some regions the trends were assessed individually within the scope of the pre-stakeholder questionnaire. The results were presented in the workshop and discussed, with hardly any objections. The susceptibility indicators and drivers were also presented and discussed during the workshop. Susceptibility scores were obtained by individual completion of an online survey during the workshop (through real-time survey tools that enable an interactive and engaging experience). Participants confirmed the relevance of the drivers.
- In other regions, trends and sensitivity were obtained in the workshop. For the trend, there was no prior discussion and participants completed individually through real-time survey tools their perception of the trends. In the case of sensitivity, there was a discussion. Initially the susceptibility indicators were presented and then the perception of the trend was discussed. For some drivers there was consensus, and for others there were more diverse points of view.

The regional MAPs were consulted on **whether it had been possible to obtain a prioritised list of adaptive capacity mechanisms**. They stressed that:

- Most of the coordinators answered positively. The mechanisms were initially identified during the interviews and subsequently discussed, completed, validated and prioritised during the workshop.
- For the prioritisation, many followed the guidelines facilitated by the Work Package leader. Participants used a whiteboard and stickers to indicate their preferred mechanisms.
- At the workshop, each participant was asked to vote for the preferred mechanisms. Finally, the most voted for mechanisms were included in the priority list.
- Other coordinators organised a focus group with an evaluation system that consisted of prioritising each participant's proposals with the help of stickers. For each proposal, listed on the whiteboard, participants were asked to place colour-coded stickers.
- Specific coordinators expressed that they did not obtain the list during the semi-structured interviews but in the workshop associated with the task, adaptive capacity mechanisms were discussed.

Finally, linked to task 3.3, the regional MAPs coordinators were asked **whether the feasibility analysis of the adaptive capacity mechanisms had been validated with stakeholders**. Although validation was foreseen in this task, given the COVID situation, and in order to favour validation in a face-to-face workshop, it has been postponed. Adaptive capacity mechanisms will be incorporated in WP6 workshops (Scenario Analysis), where we will be able to deeply discuss and validate them with our MAP members.

In relation to **task 4.4 Participatory Workshops in each region (appraisal of vulnerability and performance of value chains)**, MAPs coordinators were asked to reflect on:

The **presentation of the results of task 4.3** to the MAP in a face-to-face workshop **as a preliminary conceptual "map" of the VC and the system**. Their responses include:

- All the coordinators presented the results of the previous task 4.3.
- Some indicated that they thought about how best to translate the results into accessible language in a way that would start a conversation among MAP members about the work done in the previous months. They tried the format of challenges and opportunities.
- Most indicated that they showed the diagrams to the participants of the face-to-face workshop. It was useful for participants to have a physical element on which to base conversations, but the diagrams were perhaps still too complex. Some coordinators therefore adopted a simplified version. In some cases, they were useful for setting up the working groups on the four steps of the value chain: production, processing, distribution/marketing, and consumption.
- Other coordinators explained that during the interviews they presented the diagram to each interviewee, so that everyone was familiar with it. At the beginning of the face-to-face workshops, they presented some of the results found during the interviews, but then they gave the participants an almost empty diagram and worked on it in smaller groups.

Finally, regarding task 4.4, the coordinators were asked **whether the participants used their local knowledge to update understanding and illustrate whether there are still gaps in the coexistence of the system and the value chain**. They replied that:

- All coordinators answered yes. In general, The MAP members were willing to participate and add their own knowledge and experience to the analysis. They all brought a lot of additional local knowledge. The diversity of points of view favoured this social learning exercise.
- In some cases, despite the involvement of MAP actors, there were difficulties in carrying out an accurate feasibility analysis. Some participants left the workshop before its end, which limits the possibility of an accurate discussion. Also, because for some speakers there were no real discoveries and the links between the value chain and territorial capital remain little known and appreciated.

For the activities related to **consultations and interviews to experts** MAPs have carried out tasks 3.3 and 4.3 during the first two years of the project.

In relation to **task 3.3 Consultation of 8-10 experts**, as well as local actors, such as farmers and forestry owners, MAP coordinators were asked to reflect on:

How the initial discourse during consultations and expert interviews helped to generate interest in the project. The coordinators reflected that:

- The MAP coordinators responded positively. Some of the MAPs did not simply present the project but adapted the narrative to the interviewee (anticipating topics of interest to them).

- Other coordinators alluded to the relevance to the project's claim for policy change, value chain knowledge or improved planning capacity for the region. Some MAPs focused the initial discourse on the fact that one of the objectives of the project is to be able to influence European policies so that they really know and take into account their reality, and how these policies can help them address the challenges ahead.
- Others focused on the fact that in their area there is a lack of knowledge about the local value chain and a lack of planning capacity. It was remarked that working with local communities could improve planning capacity and consequently increase funding opportunities, resilience and sustainability.

The coordinators were also asked **whether research-related issues (e.g. baseline variable, drivers of change, components, mechanisms of adaptive capacity) were well understood by the stakeholders.** Their responses include:

- The coordinators' reflections explained different situations. Questions were well understood by stakeholders and they did provide relevant information for the research. The biggest difficulty, during the semi-structured interviews, was probably trying not to fatigue the stakeholder, since they should be asked questions on several drivers of change.
- For some coordinators it was a big challenge to translate certain concepts into the native language and into terms that could be understood by stakeholders. Therefore, there was an adaptation for the stakeholders to understand correctly what was asked of them and to provide the right information.
- On some occasions, participants were diverted from the topic, as they needed to discuss other issues related to the value chain. In general, it was time-consuming to connect participants' concerns with the project's objective, but in many cases participants were willing to comment on the project structure and offered some valuable insights.

Finally, **it was asked whether the interview phase was useful in generating stakeholder commitment to the project.** They replied that:

- All coordinators indicated that it was very important for building trust and closeness. The interviewee was also able to ask questions and learn more about the project, and this promotes greater commitment to the project.
- The data collection phase, and especially documentation and reporting, was very well planned. The interview guide with the report sheet was especially useful for both online and face-to-face interviews. The interviews gave an opportunity to talk to people who would otherwise have been difficult to approach.
- Furthermore, it facilitated interviewees to provide new contacts and thereby strengthen the composition of the MAP.

In relation to task 4.3 Extended value chain analysis, MAPs coordinators were asked to reflect on VC stakeholders underrepresented. The MAP coordinators mentioned different types of actors such as: researchers, national level representatives, local production, farmers and other production actors, small enterprises, local-level processing and distribution of the final product, the innovation intermediary/advisor, the retail trade, and the consumer. Several coordinators highlighted the lack of women and young people.

4.2.3. Activity in the Virtual Research Environment

The MOVING VREs are built on the D4Science Infrastructure⁴ by exploiting the gCube open-source technology (Assante *et al.* 2019a, Assante *et al.* 2019b). From the end-user point of view, it manifests in the MOVING Gateway (accessible at <https://moving.d4science.org/>), the access point to the services and Virtual Research Environments available to the MOVING community.

For a better communication with, and between, the regional MAP coordinators a dedicated Virtual Research Environment (VRE) is available on the MOVING Gateway starting from the second part of June 2021.

The VRE is the main digital working platform for the Consortium and the participants in the EU MAP. The CNR (National Research Council) deploys and technically operates the VRE that supports two-way communication with the members, exchanges, storage, social networking, activity trackers, and more functionalities.

In Figure 7, the overall number of users benefitting from the facilities offered by the Regional MAP VRE is reported, i.e., as of June 2022, the VRE is serving 61 users.

⁴ D4Science Infrastructure: www.d4science.org

Figure 7. Regional MAP VRE users

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 8 reports the overall number of working sessions initiated per month via the MOVING Gateway. Up to June 2022, more than 800 working sessions have been executed by the users, with an average of 60+ working sessions per month.

Figure 8. Regional MAP VRE working sessions

Source: MOVING H2020

The MOVING Regional MAP VRE is also used as a social space where messages can be posted to all members. Figure 9, Figure 10 and Figure 11 report the overall exploitation of the Social Interaction facilities for this VRE.

Figure 9. MOVING Regional MAP VRE Social Interaction posts

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 10. MOVING Regional MAP VRE Social Interaction likes

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 11. MOVING Regional MAP VRE Social Interaction replies

Source: MOVING H2020

4.2.4. Barriers and challenges of regional MAPs

The main barriers and challenges identified for the regional MAPs are compiled in Table 7.

Table 7. Barriers and challenges for regional MAPs

Barriers and challenges	
MAP functioning and effectiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keep initial energy, resources and time for MAP of new creation. • Certain products and services in the selected value chains did not have a pre-defined sector, which makes it difficult to create the MAP. • COVID-19 has discouraged in-person meetings. • Distances to go to a face-to-face meeting. • Overload of online meetings. • Lack of familiarity with digital technologies. • Workload of practitioners: overlap with harvesting times or other agrarian practices such as milking. • Availability of farmers and business actors. • Lack of experience of some actors to express themselves in multidisciplinary groups. • Lack of the information and difficulty of the project's activities. • Convey the complex content; make the terminology and objectives understood. • Lack of clear compensation for participants' effort (use of their time, offer useful results to participants, etc.). • Conflicting interests among the regional actors.
Balance representation of actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group(s) of actor(s) underrepresented: i. Business, retailers, processors and distribution; ii. Farmers; iii. Public sector, especially policymakers from the national level; iv. Young people; v. Women (gender relations-representation in the sector); and vi. NGO/CSOs and civil society, as well as channelling a more systemic understanding of consumers views. • Identify and contact people from unrepresented groups. • Take advantage of interviews to strengthen the MAP. • Approach young people (secondary schools, universities). • Approach women. • Select the venue to facilitate participation of all type of actors.
Main issues to carry out the activities foreseen in the workplan for	<p>Interest of MAP members:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish a close relationship with MAP members.

regional MAPs and needs for inclusions of new activities

- Keep motivation levels high and make the unique value of MOVING clear to stakeholders.
- The long project implementation period does not help to keep stakeholders' interest alive, as they receive fragmented and temporally separated information.
- The conceptual complexity of the project does not help to convey information and encourage active participation of MAP members.
- The need to have a local partner who can act as an intermediary between "us" (researchers coming from outside) and "them" (local stakeholders and especially producers).
- Workload of MAP coordinators.
- Lack of time for MAP members to meet and cooperate.
- Lack of interest of key stakeholders in the area to participate in projects.
- Need for training of farmers to help them form a network and respond to their needs.

Composition of the MAPs:

- Have a balanced composition of MAP members.
- Balance between the presence of research actors (different institutions and projects) and producers/stakeholders in general.
- Gender imbalance in the MAPs.
- Involvement of young people in the MAP.

Content:

- Lack of detailed knowledge of the specific value chain.
- Some actors (farmers, local stakeholders) believe that they do not know enough about the value chain to participate in the analysis.
- Reach joint analyses with actors with different views on resource management and, in general, on the value chain.
- Institutional environment.

Language:

- Lack of knowledge of English.
- Need to provide some summaries in the national language to MAP members to give them some information and maintain their interest in the project.

Location:

- Find a venue in the Mountain Reference Landscape suitable for all participants.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to think and prepare well before going to the "field" and the days spent there are intense in order to be able to contact as many people as possible (e.g. for interviews). • Difficulties in holding face-to-face events.
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4.2.5. Strengths and opportunities of regional MAPs

The main strengths and opportunities identified for the regional MAPs are compiled in Table 8.

Table 8. Strengths and opportunities for regional MAPs

Strengths and opportunities	
Functioning and effectiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New network and community that have not previously interacted before. • Longer set-up period for the MAP establishment is needed. • Need and potential to link MOVING MAP objectives to the real needs of the participants/mountain community. • To improve the engagement, more fieldwork and in-person meetings needed. • Mediation is needed to reduce conflict among stakeholders.
Knowledge exchanges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional MAP consists of local stakeholders with wide practical experiences. It is an opportunity to know better other actors and learn from each other. • New communication channel and tools for MAP members (WhatsApp, other). • Strengthen the dialogue between experts and community members. • There is a high level of interest from local stakeholders on the project/work on the value chain. • Space to clarify that different business models/sectors are not necessarily in conflict.
Alliances and networking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking opportunities at the value chain level. • Increase connection with other regional MAPs and the EU MAP (regional, national and international perspective). • Link the activity of the MAP to other local initiatives. • Try to link MOVING project with other projects at local level, to emphasise the possible synergies.

4.3. Monitoring the Regional MAPs

Under WP1, AEIDL has developed a monitoring and evaluation tool for MAPs to be used by the coordinators to reflect on the MAP performance and engagement. It helps to:

- Keep track of and reflect on the performance and engagement of the MAPs.
- Capture and record the information needed to feed into deliverables and the reporting on the progress of the objectives achieved, and measurable impacts of the project overall.

The tool takes the form of an Excel file with four spreadsheets: (i) Introduction; (ii) MAP composition; (iii) Activities; and (iv) Consultations and interviews. It allows the collection of quantitative information (profile of MAP members and participants of activities and consultations), as well as qualitative information through reflection and perception of the coordinating MAP and feedback from members.

Each of the MAP's coordinators updates the information on an ongoing basis. In the first two years, two common updates have been requested for all regions: in M17 (January 2022) for the M18 technical report and in M22 (June 2022) for the present D1.3.

5. European Multi-Actor Platform

The EU MAP offers an open space to stakeholders that are interested to exchange, learn and interact at the EU level on resilience to climate change, and other threats, of mountain value chains. A key purpose for the EU MAP is to support MOVING partners in the development of specific deliverables of the project, bringing the knowledge and outcomes produced from the regional MAPs and organising structured exchanges with key external actors, including representatives from regional MAPs and other EU level actors external to the MOVING consortium.

The EU MAP also supports peer-to-peer exchanges on additional topics relevant for the members and for the regional MAPs. Hence, the plan for the activities of the EU MAP offers a certain degree of flexibility to be able to adapt to the interests of its members.

5.1. Composition

The EU MAP gathers stakeholders interested in exploring further the topic of resilience to climate change, and other threats, of mountain value chains from an EU-wide perspective. It also enables them to contribute to the development of some of the MOVING deliverables.

Given the pan-European and international nature of the MOVING project and the EU MAP, the main language used in all types of interaction is English, which might be a limiting factor for the engagement of some local stakeholders.

Interested members from the 23 regional MAPs have been encouraged to join the EU MAP, to share their experiences and outcomes developed within the regional MAPs.

In addition, the EU MAP engaged external stakeholder from policy, research and relevant practice groups working in other Member States or at EU level.

Until M22, the total number of members of the EU MAP is 48 stakeholders, of which 54% are women and 46% are men.

Figure 12. EU MAP composition (type of actor, =48)

Source: MOVING H2020

Although gender representation is balanced, there is a strong representation of researchers in the EU MAP. Some conclusions and actions point can be concluded:

- The working language of the EU MAP is English. This makes certain stakeholder groups feel more comfortable participating in the MAP.

In order to improve the representation of stakeholder types such as farmers, advisors or from business further information work will be carried out through the regional MAPs.

- The types of actions developed so far (webinars, blogs, contributions to public consultations) have attracted more researchers.

Further practice exchange activities are envisaged among regional MAPs and thematic clusters (aligned with the work in WP5 and WP6) so that it can be an incentive for other types of actors.

5.2. Performance and engagement

The activities proposed for the EU MAP are designed to:

- Contribute to key MOVING deliverables by bringing a pan-European perspective from stakeholders across the continent;
- Identify the main focus and interest of the community and mobilise stakeholders to be part of the community;
- Create a long-lasting community that can continue after the project ends.

5.2.1. Setting up the EU MAP

The EU MAP carried out at early stages of the project the following activities to support the set-up of the MAP:

- **Mapping of key stakeholders** to identify relevant actors working around mountain value chains, who can potentially complement and enrich the discussions with valuable knowledge and information for the MOVING community.

Stakeholder mapping was planned in the CoP work plan as a fundamental part of establishing and running the EU MAP. The work plan is an internal document that was co-designed with all project partners in early 2021.

Up to M18 (PR1) 120 stakeholders were identified and it is a work that continues over time and that today has already 163 mapped actors.

The mapping is done on the basis of interest and influence logic. AEIDL looked for key actors in the field, experts from recent papers/studies on the topic, speakers at related events in recent years, etc. For each of them AEIDL detailed: name, type of stakeholder, main focus of work, relevant information, country, contact details.

Each of them has been contacted before the establishment of the EU MAP to present the project, to invite them to join the CoP-EU MAP, to serve as a platform for their work, to participate in the EU MAP webinars. Table 9 shows the total of stakeholders mapped by country and Table 10 by type of stakeholder.

Table 9. Total of stakeholders mapped by country

Country	Number of stakeholders mapped
Andorra	3
Austria	15
Belgium	4

Canada	2
Finland	1
France	12
Germany	13
Greece	2
Italy	23
Macedonia	1
Norway	1
Poland	1
Portugal	4
Romania	4
Slovenia	3
Spain	14
Switzerland	17
Turkey	1
United Kingdom	15
Several countries	27
Total	163

Source: MOVING H2020

Table 10. Total of stakeholders mapped by type of stakeholder

Type of stakeholder	Number of stakeholders mapped
Researcher	79
NGO/association/foundation	31
EU-funded projects (H2020, Horizon Europe, LIFE, Interreg, etc.)	10
Public authority/policy-maker	12

Business (diversified or non-agricultural businesses)	3
Other	28
Total	163

Source: MOVING H2020

- **Mapping of interests and expectations from MOVING and other relevant stakeholders.** The stakeholders' interests and expectations has been collected through a **survey** among MOVING partners to capture their views (project coordinator, WP leaders, coordinators of the regional MAPs), as well as targeted **interviews** with some MOVING partners and external stakeholders.

To this end, a first survey was circulated to the project partners in August 2021 and 20 responses were received. This survey was targeted at all MOVING partners in order to collect ideas, expectations and suggestions from them and their potential regional MAP members (as some of the regional MAPs were still being formed). The results supported the definition of the scope of some EU MAP activities.

Furthermore, a total of 6 interviews with key informants have taken place. These were: Euromontana, Mountain Research Initiative (MRI) and GEO Mountains, Mountains Partnership, FAO, the EU-funded LIFE MIDMACC (Mid-mountain adaptation to climate change) project, Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO) in Portugal, and the Association of European Regions for Products of Origin (AREPO). See the details of these interviews in the section 5.2.2 “Implementation of activities” in this report.

The whole mapping exercise helped to identify some relevant stakeholders, organisations and experts that might be interested to engage in the EU MAP and to further reflect on the scope of some of the activities and define new ones that might be relevant.

5.2.2. Implementation of activities

Activities carried out by EU MAP include interviews and creation of alliances with key informants from mapped stakeholders, organisation of thematic webinars, contribution to EC public consultations, campaigning, preparation of blogs and articles, and preparation of information materials.

Interviews with key informants

To facilitate the establishment of the EU MAP, AEIDL interviewed 6 key informants. The following tables show the details and results of these interviews.

Table 11. EU MAP Interview with Euromontana

Key interview points	Responses
Organisation/project interviewed	Euromontana
Date	29/09/2021
Type of actor	European organisation
Motivation	Euromontana is part of the advisory board of MOVING. It is also a key player at European level in relation to its work on sustainable development of mountain areas in the last two decades.
Key areas of the interviewee's work	<p>Euromontana focuses its work on fostering sustainable development of mountain areas based on: economic development; human capital; natural and heritage resources; services and networks; culture and traditions and policies; and governance in mountain areas.</p> <p>Euromontana fulfils its duty by implementing the following four types of actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Representing mountain communities. • Promoting the strengths of mountain areas and the added value for Europe of sustainable investment in these areas. • Organising cooperation between mountain peoples. • Carry out, participate in or compile studies.
Possible synergies with MOVING	<p>Particular interest was given to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organise an activity on mountain value chains analysis, especially related to the findings of deliverable D4.1 Inventory of Mountain Value Chains. The interviewee expressed the need for further definition in the inventory by type of value chain (VC), by thematic cluster. In addition, reflect on the extent to which good practices and innovations have been identified, as well as on whether the quality term "mountain product" has been considered. • The planned long-term strategy of the MOVING Community of Practice. • The EU MAP to develop some thematic activity on new technologies and their application to mountain areas, and links

	<p>to the opportunities for these areas in the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation and presentation of results at Euromontana and MOVING events.
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Source: MOVING H2020

Table 12. EU MAP Interview with Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO)

Key interview points	Responses
Organisation/project interviewed	Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO)
Date	7/10/2021
Type of actor	Research Centre
Motivation	<p>CIMO is a multidisciplinary research unit focused on Mediterranean mountain issues based at the Polytechnic Institute of Bragança (Portugal) and with a unit at the Polytechnic Institute of Viana do Castelo (Portugal). In addition, CIMO is part of the national research network coordinated by the Portuguese Science and Technology Foundation (FCT).</p> <p>CIMO aims to promote research in Mediterranean mountain areas according to the best international practices, promoting scientific observation and experimental development for the conservation, exploitation and scientific valorisation of biodiversity, natural resources, farming and forest systems, and mountain products; to develop sustainable land use systems, improving endogenous research competencies; and linking research and stakeholders promoting sustainable development in mountain areas.</p>
Key areas of the interviewee's work	<p>CIMO is organised around two main research groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Socio Ecological Systems. • Sustainable Processes and Products.
Possible synergies with MOVING	<p>Particular interest was given to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Follow the work in the two Portuguese Mountain Reference Regions of the MOVING project, and other regions with selected wine-related value chains.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be part of the EU MAP. • Valorisation of resources and innovations applied to production in value chains. • Participation and presentation of results at CIMO and MOVING events.
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Source: MOVING H2020

Table 13. EU MAP Interview with Mountain Partnership

Key interview points	Responses
Organisation/project interviewed	Mountain Partnership
Date	13/10/2021
Type of actor	International organisation
Motivation	<p>The Mountain Partnership is a United Nations voluntary alliance of partners dedicated to improving the lives of mountain peoples and protecting mountain environments around the world.</p> <p>Founded in 2002, the Mountain Partnership addresses the challenges facing mountain regions by tapping the wealth and diversity of resources, knowledge, information and expertise, from and between its members, in order to stimulate concrete initiatives at all levels that will ensure improved quality-of-life and environments in the world's mountain regions.</p>
Key areas of the interviewee's work	<p>The Mountain Partnership is a platform for joint action and programmes. It focuses on working together for mountain peoples and environments:</p> <p>Advocate for global attention:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leading international campaigns and holding events to highlight mountain issues globally. • Ensuring that sustainable mountain development is included in global, regional and national negotiations and policies. • Drafting policy and issues briefs, key messages and United Nations (UN) reports. <p>Promote joint projects:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing information about project calls and funding opportunities. • Creating an enabling environment to foster collaboration among members. • Supporting members to develop joint proposals and projects. <p>Share knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Producing technical publications, a website, brochures, videos and newsletters. • Conducting research and analysis of data for evidence building. • Fostering communication among members. <p>Strengthen capacity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conducting the annual International Programme on Research and Training on Sustainable Management of Mountain Areas (IPROMO) course. • Encouraging technology transfer among members • Organising workshops and training sessions.
<p>Possible synergies with MOVING</p>	<p>Particular interest was given to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be part of the EU MAP. • Collaborate in communication and awareness-raising activities linked to International Mountain Day. • Participation and presentation of results at Mountain Partnership and MOVING events, especially bringing the global perspective and looking at good practices.

Source: MOVING H2020

Table 14. EU MAP Interview with AREPO

Key interview points	Responses
<p>Organisation/project interviewed</p>	<p>Association of European Regions for Products of Origin (AREPO)</p>
<p>Date</p>	<p>21/10/2021</p>
<p>Type of actor</p>	<p>European organisation</p>

<p>Motivation</p>	<p>AREPO is one of the 23 MOVING partners. AREPO is a network of regions and producer associations that deals with products of origin.</p> <p>AREPO aims to promote and defend the interests of producers and consumers of European regions involved in the valorisation of quality food products.</p> <p>AREPO's main contribution to the MOVING project is linked to the dissemination of project results (both at EU and regional level). Thanks to its regional contacts, AREPO can reach local producers and producer associations, as well as other relevant regional targets.</p> <p>As a European institutional network, recognised as an expert in the area of EU Quality Schemes by the European Commission, AREPO will contribute to policy assessment thanks to its regional expertise at multinational level in the implementation of CAP measure and quality policy. Furthermore, AREPO involves relevant regional/local authorities, producer associations/consortia, as well as relevant operational groups implemented in the project's regions.</p>
<p>Key areas of the interviewee's work</p>	<p>AREPO's work focuses on:</p> <p>Regions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The development of Geographical Indications and quality products as tools for rural development and territorial planning. • This also requires the strengthening of EU policy on Geographical Indications and derived products. <p>Producers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The guarantee of good income conditions for producers. • Lobbying for an adequate protection of products of origin on the European market as well as on third markets. • Lobbying to ensure that quality finds its proper place within promotion policies. <p>Consumers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring appropriate communication and accurate information.
<p>Possible synergies with MOVING</p>	<p>Particular interest was given to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be part of the EU MAP. • Support the communication and dissemination of the project as well as networking activities. • Co-organise with the EU MAP of the MOVING CoP a thematic webinar on EU quality schemes: the added value for mountain

	<p>value chains. It will be organised in autumn 2022 with the aim to: (i) provide an update of the new EU quality policy, according to the EC legislative proposals, and the implications to mountain value chains; and (ii) inform about the implementation and added value of the EU quality schemes and the implications for mountain value chains.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publicise results of the organisation's work, such as the sustainability guideline.
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Source: MOVING H2020

Table 15. EU MAP Interview with Mountain Research Initiative

Key interview points	Responses
Organisation/project interviewed	Mountain Research Initiative (MRI)
Date	25/10/2021
Type of actor	International organisation
Motivation	<p>For more than two decades, the MRI has served as a coordination network for research collaboration, bringing the global mountain research community together. The MRI promotes basic and applied research to understand how drivers and processes of global change present challenges and opportunities in mountain social-ecological systems.</p> <p>Through the convening role of the MRI Coordination Office, the MRI has initiated numerous collaborations and networks of researchers, implementing actions that enhance the profile and value of global change research in mountains, whilst also integrating and synthesising the results of this research and thereby informing stakeholders about the implications of these results for policy and practice.</p>
Key areas of the interviewee's work	<p>The MRI envisions a world in which research to identify and understand drivers and processes of global change in mountains is promoted and linked across disciplines and mountain regions worldwide. The MRI works to :</p>

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify and understand mountain social ecological systems (components, elements, interactions, and trends) via long-term empirical observations and modelling. 2. Identify visions and substantiate targets that reflect and sustain vibrant mountain social-ecological systems, where sustainability outcomes are aspired to and their trade-offs are defined in context. 3. Enable pathways and transformations to sustainability by identifying, assessing, and supporting decisions, policies, and actions, as well as their fitness-for-purpose in closing the problem-solution gap, specific to diverse mountain contexts, from the observed changes (systems knowledge) to the desired outcomes (target knowledge).
<p>Possible synergies with MOVING</p>	<p>Particular interest was given to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Synergies between the MOVING Community of Practice and the MRI Community-Led Activities and working groups. Both could bring an intergroup dimension. • The MRI is interested in learning about the methodological and analytical results from the vulnerability assessment related to WP3 carried out in MOVING in order to understand: (i) selected value chain frameworks; the impact of climate change and the data used and data gaps in vulnerability analyses. Also, the projections generated related to the future foresight exercise. A potential webinar could be organised by MOVING. • Participation and presentation of results at MRI and GEO Mountains and MOVING events.

Source: MOVING H2020

Table 16. EU MAP Interview with LIFE MIDMACC project

Key interview points	Responses
<p>Organisation/project interviewed</p>	<p>LIFE MIDMACC project</p>
<p>Date</p>	<p>16/12/2021</p>
<p>Type of actor</p>	<p>EU funded project</p>

<p>Motivation</p>	<p>This project promotes adaptation through the implementation and testing of different landscape management measures to meet climate change related challenges in marginal mid-mountain areas of Spain (La Rioja, Aragon and Catalonia), while improving their socioeconomic development.</p> <p>It covers diverse bioclimatic conditions, from the sub-humid Mediterranean of the Pyrenees to the sub-Mediterranean mid-mountains of the Iberian Mountain Range.</p>
<p>Key areas of the interviewee's work</p>	<p>LIFE MIDMACC focuses its work on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing landscape adaptation measures in marginal mid-mountain areas in order to improve their environmental and socioeconomic resilience to climate change. • Assessing the socio-economic and ecological effectiveness of the applied measures through widespread monitoring and modelling. • Involving the regional managers and stakeholders in the design, development and evaluation of adaptation measures, through decision-making regional committees. • Engaging the governments of La Rioja, Aragon and Catalonia in the creation of a coordinated policy framework that improves the sustainable use of mid-mountain areas. • Developing integrated Climate Change Adaptation Guidelines for mid-mountain areas. • Carrying out awareness and capacity building activities on adaptation to climate change at local and regional level. • Supporting the application and further development of European policies related to climate change adaptation in mountainous rural areas.
<p>Possible synergies with MOVING</p>	<p>Particular interest was given to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be part of the EU MAP. • Support the communication and dissemination of the project as well as networking activities. • Participation and presentation of results at LIFE MIDMACC and MOVING events, especially concerning the barriers identified for certain agricultural practices in mountain areas, action measures for adaptation to climate change in mid-mountain areas and the economic revival of the area, vulnerability analysis. A potential webinar could be organised by MOVING.

Source: MOVING H2020

Webinars

MOVING organised its [first EU MAP webinar](#) on Mountain Value Chains: heterogeneity and innovation on 16 December 2021. The event gathered around 60 attendees from different backgrounds (research, public authorities, advisors, business, producers, other EU-funded projects, etc.) from 18 countries.

The main objectives of this webinar were to:

1. Present the MOVING project and publicise the EU MAP;
2. Showcase specific traditional or emerging value chains working on innovation and resilience to climate change;
3. Enhance the exchange, learn and interact at the EU level on heterogeneity and innovation in mountain value chains.

During the webinar, two presentations focused on the first year of progress and results of the project and its Community of Practice (CoP). Within the MOVING CoP, the European Multi-Actor Platform (EU MAP) was presented. The event featured other presentations on mountain value chains of three project [reference regions](#), which showed the heterogeneity and different levels of innovation: (i) Los Pedroches PDO Iberian Ham value chain; (ii) Speyside Malt Whisky value chain; and (iii) Certified ecotourism Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains value chain.

All the [presentations](#) and [recordings](#) of this MOVING webinar are available on the [event page](#). The [highlights report](#) is available on the website and in [Zenodo](#).

The [second webinar](#) is organised for 8 November 2022. The [agenda](#) and [event information](#) can be found on the MOVING website, and they have been disseminated in the June 2022 newsletter and on social media. It can be found in the [events calendar of the Mountain Partnership FAO](#) for the International Mountain Day of 2022. It will deal with the topic of European Quality schemes: the added value for mountain value chains.

Additional activities

In addition, MOVING carried out other additional activities, which are compiled in Table 17.

Table 17. EU MAP additional activities

Activity	Description	Timing
Contributions to open	Contribution to the EU Roadmap restoring sustainable carbon cycles (news item and full contribution)	October 2021
	Contribution and support of Mountain Education and Innovation Manifesto (MEIM)	November 2021

consultations and other processes	Brain drain – mitigating challenges associated with population decline (news item and full contribution)	June 2021
	Sustainable EU food system –new initiative	July 2021
Campaigns	Why an International Mountain Day? A video was prepared for the International Mountain Day on 11 December 2021, MOVING Working on 23 Mountain Reference Regions and launched on Facebook with a total of 95 views and 330 people reached; and on Twitter with a total of 170 views and 793 impressions.	December 2021
	For International Women's Day: The importance of women in the sustainability of mountain areas	March 2022
Infographics	International Mountain Day Retrospective	December 2021
	MOVING's contribution to the EU Long-term vision for rural areas (LTVRA)	May 2021
Blog articles and news item	See all blog articles here and news item here .	During the whole period (year 1 and 2).

5.2.3. Activity in the Virtual Research Environment

For the functioning of the EU MAP, relationships between the members need to be established to enable them to exchange knowledge and learn from each other. For that, a dedicated Virtual Research Environment (VRE) is available on the MOVING Gateway, which was launched in November 2021.

The VRE is the main digital working platform for the Consortium and the participants in the EU MAP. The CNR (National Research Council) deploys and technically operates the VRE, which supports two-way communication with the members, exchanges, storage, social networking, activity trackers, and more functionalities.

Stakeholders from the project and external actors are able to join the EU MAP by filling in a specific [form](#), embedded on the website in a specific [section](#) for the Community of Practice. The form also allows for the provision of consent for the use of data, complying with GDPR.

In Figure 13, the overall number of users benefitting from the facilities offered by the EU MAP VRE is reported, as of June 2022, the VRE is serving nearly 50 users.

Figure 13. EU MAP VRE users

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 14 reports the overall number of working sessions initiated per month via the MOVING Gateway. Up to June 2022, more than 300 working sessions have been executed by the users, with an average of 40 working sessions per month.

Figure 14. EU MAP VRE working sessions

Source: MOVING H2020

The MOVING EU MAP VRE is also used as a social space where messages can be posted to all members. Figure 15, Figure 16 and Figure 17 report the overall exploitation of the Social Interaction facilities for this VRE.

Figure 15. MOVING VRE Social Interaction posts

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 16. MOVING VRE Social Interaction likes

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 17. MOVING VRE Social Interaction replies

Source: MOVING H2020

5.2.4. Barriers and challenges of the EU MAP

The main barriers and challenges for the implementation, functioning and performance of the EU MAP are compiled in Table 18.

Table 18. Barriers and challenges for the EU MAP

Barriers and challenges	
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of time to participate in the activities. • Availability of technologies. • Lack of compensation. • Regional public administrations are usually overcapacity and understaffed.
Functioning and effectiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heterogeneity of the possible group. • Lack of motivation to join virtually. • Mistrust towards research (if it comes across as top-down).
Language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The use of English for local and regional actors.

Knowledge exchanges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less interest given the difficulty in the applicability of certain topics (legislation, quality systems) for countries outside Europe. • Keeping members' interest with topics that are really practical for them. • Transdisciplinary boundaries. • Relevance of the topics addressed (need to offer something tangible).
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5.2.5. Strengths, opportunities and motivation to join the EU MAP

The main strengths and opportunities for the implementation, functioning and performance of the EU MAP are summarised in Table 19.

Table 19. Strengths and opportunities for the EU MAP

Strengths and opportunities	
Functioning and effectiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To know the profile of EU MAP members and their expertise.
Knowledge exchange	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn from research outcomes of MOVING. • The role of training is the key point to the success of the MAP. • Exchange with other stakeholders in similar positions and inspiring experiences. • Exchange with peers from other parts of Europe. • Knowing how other actors have solved a problem or if there are any synergies will help to broaden horizons. • Learn about EU-level policies and strategies. • Learn from a number of EU examples. • Learn about good practices and opportunities in other countries.

Given these opportunities, AEIDL has collected data from members on their motivation for joining the EU MAP. It consulted in the first and second survey on ideas and expectations of the CoP, as well as in the form for expressing interest in joining the EU MAP.

Figure 18 shows the distribution of responses among the options in percentages. Project partners and external actors consider as most relevant for joining the EU MAP the possibility of finding ideas and practical examples (68.4%), followed by learning from research outcomes of MOVING or other initiatives (63.2%), and meeting and learning from others (63.2%). The motivation of exchange of knowledge and information (articles, news, events) was selected by 42.1% of respondents.

In addition, 15.8% of respondents selected other reasons, such as: to be in contact with other projects applying the interactive innovation approach, to connect Horizon multi-actor projects and to learn about MOVING methods and results due to the engagement in a rural mid-mountain area.

Figure 18. Main motivation to join the EU MAP

Source: MOVING H2020

5.2.6. Thematic areas and topics to focus upcoming EU MAP activities

In the surveys carried out in August 2021, and in May and June 2022, about ideas and expectations for the EU MAP and the CoP, respondents indicated their thematic preference for upcoming EU MAP activities. Figure 19 shows the percentage of respondents who have selected a number of topics provided in the survey.

Figure 19. Preference of thematic areas and topics for upcoming EU MAP webinars

Source: MOVING H2020

In order of preference, the topics for the following webinars would be:

- Innovation in governance systems in mountain areas (63.2%).
- Mountain areas and the long-term vision for rural areas (57.9%).
- Engaging youth of mountain areas in the long-term vision for rural areas (57.9%).
- EU Quality schemes: the added value for mountain value chains (52.6%).
- Internal meeting of EU MAP members: getting to know each other and defining new activities (47.4%).
- Women move mountains (aligned with International Mountains Day of 2022) (42.1%).
- Mountain areas and the added value of the protected natural sites (36.8%)
- Mountain Value Chains: heterogeneity and innovation (a second event presenting other MOVING value chains) (31.6%).

Additional themes were noted in the 'Other' response:

- MOVING conceptual framework and methods.
- Adaptation to climate change.
- Impact of the agri-environmental measures of the Common Agricultural Policy in mountain areas.
- Nature conservation, landscape protection and agri-biodiversity policy-related topics.

- The roles and the contribution of Geoparks and the Emblematic Mediterranean Mountains.
- Nature-Based Solutions.
- Identification and assessment of factors that affect the degradation of mountains.
- How to better link private initiative with public intervention.
- How to valorise social capital through value chains.
- Quality brands and labels.
- Interconnection of production sectors.
- Rural tourism in mountains areas.
- Examples of mountain value chains in the European context.
- Innovation in mountain areas.
- Mechanisms to promote cooperation.
- Traditional and sustainable know-how.
- Future foresight for mountain areas.
- Policies in general related to mountains.

5.2.7. Relevant knowledge, initiative, project or experience to share in the EU MAP

Partners and external actors were asked about knowledge, experiences, relevant results, initiatives or projects they would like to share in the EU MAP. Among the responses, the following issues stand out:

- Geographical Indications, such as protected designation of origin (PDO) and protected geographical indication (PGI).
- Common Agricultural Policy Strategic Plans.
- Agri-environmental schemes.
- Culture, traditional practices, conservation and promotion of the local mountain ecosystems.
- Pastures conservation.
- Traditional practices on cheese-making value chains.
- Traditional practices on wine value chains.
- Work on branding of whisky sector and tourism value chains.
- Work in the bio-honey value chain as there is a high interconnection at territorial level (agriculture, forestry, recreational use of rural space, climate change, etc.).
- New technologies for climate change adaptation and mitigation.
- Innovative ways of direct marketing.
- How cooperative efforts have more effect compared to individual efforts.
- Governance, organisational development and creation of communities.
- Facilitation of youth engagement.
- Usefulness of sharing the digital stories.

- Scientific inputs on regional (non-mountain) food value chains through various research projects.
- Co-innovation and Multi-Actor Platforms (see project [LIAISON](#). An EU-funded ‘research and innovation’ project that aims to help unlock the potential of “working in partnership for innovation” in agriculture, forestry and rural business).
- Low-intensity grazing, sheep farming and shepherds for nature conservation (see [project](#) Protect Shepherd Network - Netzwerk Schäfer schützen).
- Integrated values-based food chains (see [project](#) HealthyGrowth).

5.3. Monitoring the EU MAP

In order to refine the approach while running the EU MAP, and to draw on and share the lessons learned, it is important to monitor the ongoing activities and their effects, and to assess the process regularly. Monitoring and evaluation are intrinsic parts of co-creation and co-learning in MAPs, and therefore an ongoing part of the EU MAP process.

The following indicators (Table 20), included in the internal CoP’s workplan, support the monitoring of the activities and actions conducted within the EU MAP, and the assessment of the value and relevance of its work and interactions.

Table 20. EU MAP indicators integrated in the CoP workplan

Specific objective	Indicators (with indicative targets)	M22
Build a long-lasting community with MOVING stakeholders that is recognised as an important forum for issues around mountain value chains	Number of members in the EU MAP (target more than 200 members with a balanced representation of types of stakeholders and at least 25% women)	48 stakeholders of which 54% are women. Regarding composition: 54% researchers 15% NGO 11% CSO 8% Public authority/policymakers 4% Advisor/innovation broker/intermediary 2% Business 2% EU-funded projects 4% Others

	At least 50% of the EU MAP members find their engagement in the community useful.	It will be calculated for D1.7 and next reporting periods.
Foster the exchange of knowledge and experience that enhances expertise on mountain value chains	At least 50% of EU MAP members feel better informed about climate and environmental impacts on their livelihoods and mountain value chains.	It will be calculated for D1.7 and next reporting periods.
	Number of participants to the webinars (target more than 180 participants with a balanced representation of types of stakeholders in the total of webinars)	First webinar: 64 participants (research, public authorities, advisors, business, producers, other EU-funded projects, etc.) from 18 countries. Second webinar planned for 8 November 2022.
	Number of views of the webinars on YouTube (target more than 100 views of the total of webinars)	The five videos of the EU MAP webinar on Mountain Value Chains: heterogeneity and innovation has a total of 127 views.
	Number of posts / information shared among EU MAP members (target more than 200 posts / information shared among MOVING CoP members)	13 posts in VRE EU MAP 62 posts in VRE Regional MAPs 15 posts about CoP and EU MAP in each social media channel (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook) 5 posts about EU MAP activities on Instagram 23 posts about Regional MAPs on Instagram 3 newsletters shared with EU MAP members 1 message shared with EU MAP members by Mailchimp with the materials (presentations, recording and highlights report) from first webinar

Co-create and validate key research outputs and results delivered by MOVING	Number of outputs in which EU MAP members have contributed to their research processes	8 blog articles 2 contributions to EU public consultations (restoring carbon cycles and brain drain) 1 contribution to infographic of MOVING and the LTVRA 1 contribution to MOVING Reference Regions and natural sites (not published yet)
	At least 50% of EU MAP participants believe that the recommendations, if implemented, would increase job prospects, improve quality-of-life and contribute to the overall socio-economic development.	It will be calculated for D1.7 and next reporting periods.

Source: MOVING H2020

6. Main results of the Community of Practice by project impact

Table 21 lists the indicators included in the DoA by expected project impacts and relevant to the CoP. It includes the progress until M22 (June 2022):

Table 21. Main results of the Community of Practice

MOVING Impact	Indicators and targets	M22
Impact 1. Translate visions of future trends and dynamics and understanding of the associated drivers into strategic options for policy design, delivery and monitoring; and maximise their uptake by the relevant policy levels.	1 European Workshop with devoted sessions to new/updated policy uptake	not applicable in Y1 and Y2. Second webinar of the EU MAP is foreseen for November 2022 on EU Quality Schemes and their added value for mountain value chains. It aims to provide an update of the new EU quality policy, according to the EC legislative proposals and information for its implementation.
	Submission of evidence to EC consultations on policies of relevance to MOVING	1 Contribution to the EU Roadmap restoring sustainable carbon cycles (news item and full contribution)

		<p>1 Contribution to open consultation Brain drain – mitigating challenges associated with population decline (news item and full contribution)</p> <p>1 Contribution and support of Mountain Education and Innovation Manifesto (MEIM)</p> <p>1 MOVING's contribution to the EU Long-term vision for rural areas (LTVRA)</p> <p>1 Contribution to open consultation Sustainable EU food system –new initiative (will be submitted in July 2022)</p>
	Groups of experts (8-10) from the most noteworthy value chains for each cluster	not applicable in Y1 and Y2
	Member States make new connections: at least 5 links with other project/platforms/initiatives made	<p>SHERPA H2020</p> <p>DESIRA H2020</p> <p>Polirural H2020</p> <p>Ruralization H2020</p> <p>LIFE MIDMACC project</p> <p>SCALABLE project</p> <p>Rural Pact Platform</p> <p>Thematic Group 2.3 Mountain Research Initiative related to Essential Mountain Societal / Socio-Economic Variables</p> <p>Youth4Mountains from Mountain Partnership</p>
	80% of participants report increased awareness of potential new policy or VC options (based on CoP feedback forms)	not applicable in Y1 and Y2
	MOVING consortia invited to advise relevant EU, national or regional policy processes	<p>The project coordinator has participated in and is part of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public Hearing of the European Parliament on 16th March organised by DG AGRI/DG REGIO: "A long-term vision for the EU's rural areas" - Expert group of the thematic Group on the Long Term Rural Vision coordinated by ENRD. - Rural Pact Conference as a rapporteur of one of the sessions.

<p>Impact 2. Ensure a wide outreach and engagement in most EU Member States through a balanced and representative coverage of activities</p>	<p>>80 business actors participate in Reference Regions activities</p>	<p>Actors:</p> <p>Business (agricultural): 127 in the composition of regional MAPs and 204 participating in the activities of Y1 and Y2</p> <p>Business (diversified or non-agricultural businesses): 57 in the composition of regional MAPs and 103 participating in the activities of Y1 and Y2</p>
	<p>100 participants in the Final Policy Conference focused on policies, preferably in the European Parliament.</p>	<p>not applicable in Y1 and Y2</p>
	<p>200 members in the CoP, which include a balanced representation of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > 80 policymakers > 80 business > 25 researcher members 	<p>814 members in the CoP (regional MAPs plus EU MAP)</p> <p>106: 102 policymakers participating in the activities of Y1 and Y2 of regional MAPs plus 4 members in the EU MAP</p> <p>308: 307 business actors participating in the activities of Y1 and Y2 of regional MAPs plus 1 member of the EU MAP</p> <p>212: 186 researchers participating in the activities of Y1 and Y2 of regional MAPs plus 26 members of the EU MAP</p>
	<p>Number of participatory events:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > T3.3: 23 Regional Workshops - 300 participants > T4.4 and T4.5: 46 Regional Workshops - 300 participants > T5.3: 5 transversal workshops (one per cluster) - 35 participants > T6.2: 69 Regional Workshops (3 workshops per reference region) - 8 to 12 relevant stakeholders and external experts + 5 Cross-case workshops (one per cluster) - 20 participants + 1 pan- European experts' workshop - 25 to 40 participants 	<p>For more detail see table 5 of this deliverable.</p> <p>T3.3: 283 participants (participatory workshop) plus 290 participants (consultations)</p> <p>T4.4: 278 participants (participatory workshop). Regional MAPs of Austrian Alps and Corsica will organise the event in the coming months.</p> <p>T4.3: 355 participants (consultations)</p> <p>T4.5, T5.3 and T6.2 not applicable in Y1 and Y2</p>
<p>Impact 3. Help diversifying rural economic activities,</p>	<p>25% of women involved in CoP</p>	<p>Regional MAPs composition: 31% are women and 69% are men.</p>

<p>improving the skills base and social capital by identifying and promoting policy options which enhance the attractiveness and sustainable development of rural areas and favour generation renewal.</p> <p>Impact 4. Maintain and enhance sustainable primary production, income generated by value chains and ecosystem service delivery in mountain areas through adequate policies and integrated strategies.</p>		EU MAP composition: 54% are women and 46% are men.
	Number of young people participating in project activities: 600	<25: 33 25-40: 143
	WP7 policy outputs reflect vision and needs of young people, new migrants and women gathered in WP4 and WP6 as much as more traditional CoP participants (based on feedback on outputs)	not applicable in Y1 and Y2
	At least 80% of regional upgrading Strategies recognise synergies between VC development and protection of ecosystem services	not applicable in Y1 and Y2
	MOVING recommendations communicated to policy makers via the new post-2020 CAP Network	not applicable in Y1 and Y2
	At least 50% of CoP participants feel better informed about climate impacts on their livelihoods (based on CoP feedback forms)	not applicable in Y1 and Y2
	At least 20% of Regional MAPs business actors come from diversified or non-agricultural businesses	33.5%: 307 business actors participating in the activities of Y1 and Y2 of regional MAPs of which 103 are from diversified or non-agricultural businesses
	At least 50% of regional MAPs participants believe the policy recommendations will make their region more attractive (based on final feedback form)	not applicable in Y1 and Y2
<p>Impact 5. In the long-term proposed actions shall contribute to improving quality-of-life, socio-economic prospects, job diversity and attractiveness of rural areas</p>	Recommendations disseminated to relevant value chain actors via CoP and direct contacts	Yes, via social media, direct emails, VRE, related project, EU MAP members and mapped experts and regional MAPs coordinators.
	MOVING researchers invited to present recommendations to VC businesses or shareholders; regional development organisations or regional sustainability groups	MOVING has been presented in 28 external events from the different partners.

	At least 50% of VC actors intend to implement some or all of the MOVING recommendations	not applicable in Y1 and Y2
	At least 50% of VC actors have increased understanding of how their VC interacts with SES, impacting economic development, quality of life and the ability to adapt to climate change	not applicable in Y1 and Y2

Source: MOVING H2020

7. References

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